

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE LABOR OF CIVIL SERVANTS

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«Singapore has been successful... you need to create a system that will allow the best and most deserving people to get the jobs that need them»¹.

Lee Kuan Yew

Abstract. In this scientific article we have decided to pay attention to one of the key factors in the work of public servants, the principle of meritocracy. The principle of meritocracy in labour law relations is a system for ensuring reasonable self-discipline of employees. In this study we will analyze this factor and try to trace the peculiarity that is inherent in this system.

Keywords: form of government, meritocracy, public service, decent, professional personnel, Uzbekistan

In our opinion, meritocracy is a form of government of reasonable people who reach a position in the public service on the basis of purely personal qualities and skills, business training and wise experience. This system is alien to such human vices as «bureaucracy», «envy», «cronyism», «regionalism», «belonging to a certain family, clan», «corruption and bribery». The state apparatus based on the principle of meritocracy is prosperous, because in it everyone does what they are best at. This system corresponds to the system of State policy in the field of personnel selection and placement in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This can be seen in the fact that, according to article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On public civil service», one of the basic principles of the civil service is the principle of objectivity, professionalism and competence[6].

«The meritocratic approach promotes the inflow of highly qualified personnel into the public service, increases its prestige and can significantly affect the interest of staff in good work» (World Bank 1997, 92), because «when promotions are based on personal connections or are politicized, civil servants are more worried about catering to their superiors or influential politicians, and all efforts to raise prestige at the expense of stringent recruitment standards fail» (World Bank 1997, 93).

Meritocracy, or government of the most capable and the best, is one of the drivers of their own society and public policy of the personnel system.

¹ J. Kua. 2010. Public Administration in the Singapore Style. London, p.71

According to the meritocracy, the most capable people can achieve the best possible results and, accordingly, the public welfare of all citizens will grow. Meritocracy thus offers a fair system that achieves the best results for both the individual and society. Meritocracy provides capable and diligent people from all walks of life with the means to develop and to contribute to the well-being of society as a whole. It can be a powerful tool for social mobility and an incentive for people to do their best and reach their full potential»[2].

The idea of meritocracy implies that people are born with natural features and talents, and are not equal in birth. Hence the need to find individuals endowed with talents in a certain field and give them the means to realize their skills in order to increase the efficiency of any human activity»[3].

The next definition of meritocracy is that «Promotion in the public service is based on individual merit, which is usually seen as a combination of factors, including innate ability, hard work, proper attitude to duties and high moral character»[4].

Having determined the concept, vocation and role of meritocracy, it is worth to draw the attention of the reader that in this dissertation we will not analyze other aspects of meritocracy than the role of meritocracy in ensuring self-discipline of tax officials.

It is well known that it is easier to lead those who have sufficient skills to do so and those who are able to understand things, i.e. a competent person.

History is the main and sufficient witness that mankind, whether countries with totalitarian regimes or republics, has made every effort to ensure the discipline of public officials, as countries develop only in the direction that the head directs them to, i.e. government officials.

We believe that the principle of meritocracy, in contrast to aristocracy, bureaucracy, democracy, etc. is precisely intended to contribute most to the success of the state.

It is well known that “smart people don’t need a shepherd”; even without any disciplinary measures, they understand what needs to be done and what is not recommended to be done. Such people achieve success in the professional field through a thousand sleepless nights, as well as “blood and sweat”, therefore, they perfectly understand what deviations from the guiding ethical rules of professional activity and from legally established standards of behavior at work and in society can lead to.

Moreover, they do not have “cool” acquaintances and relatives, because they made the whole journey themselves, relying only on their own strength and efforts.

Singapore is the most successful model of a meritocratic state where the state is the prototype of a successful corporation.

In the case of Uzbekistan, the country is only in the first stages of the introduction of this system into the system of public administration, in particular in paragraph 2 of the Presidential Decree PD-5843 of 03.10.2019 «On measures to fundamentally improve the personnel policy and the system of the civil service in the Republic of Uzbekistan» said about «application of the meritocracy principle, which provides for the admission and promotion of the most worthy and capable persons on the basis of a fair and objective assessment of their professional qualities and special merits»[7].

The Decree also states that «no transparent mechanisms have been established for the selection of candidates for the civil service, **ensuring that all citizens have equal access to and progress on the basis of professional qualities and special merits**».

Summarizing all the above information, we would like to note that «the principle of meritocracy implies the creation of initially favorable conditions for objectively gifted and hard-working people, so that they in the future have a chance to occupy a high social position in the conditions of free competition»[5].

The state apparatus, based on the principle of meritocracy, is prosperous and advanced, because in it all the work is done by those who are better at it and do what they are better at doing.

Meritocracy will promote not only a broad flow of highly qualified personnel into the public service system, which will raise it to a quality new level, but the principle of meritocracy in labour law relations will act as a factor in ensuring reasonable self-discipline of employees, i.e. public servants elected on the basis of meritocracy, legal awareness and legal culture and intellectual level are at a higher level, Which is an indicator of their awareness of the consequences of insubordination of work in the public service, and they are more aware of both the positive and the negative aspects of all realities, in particular, the role of labour discipline in labour law relations, in other words, the principle of meritocracy contributes to the development of public servants' thinking in which the idea of the good of society, the idea of serving society, is paramount, where a public servant is fully aware of his or her position and role in society and of his or her own importance in the machinery of the state as the only way to realize his or her skills to the full.

In this connection, we propose to improve the legal regulation and to widely introduce all the principles of meritocracy into the system of public administration and civil service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since through the analysis of such tasks assigned to civil servants as fulfill their official duties with integrity, comply with the rules of ethical behavior established by the state body, the procedure for working with official information, as well as other rules related to the performance of the public civil service; refrain from actions (inaction) that may undermine the authority of a state body or raise doubts about the integrity of the performance of its official duties, including from any form of discrimination, bias or special disposition towards someone in the performance of their official duties; regularly improve professional competencies [6], one can understand the importance of creating the most worthy, professional corps of civil servants.

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